

A19A_2020_01
Lat: 35.157764 N
Long: 106.73066 W

A19A_2020_02
Lat: 35.158497 N
Long: 106.736865 W

A19A_2020_03
Lat: 35.158566 N
Long: 106.738482 W

A19A_2020_04
Lat: 35.158209 N
Long: 106.735805 W

A19A_2020_05
Lat: 35.158182 N
Long: 106.735662 W

A19A_2020_06
Lat: 35.158793 N
Long: 106.740172 W

A19A_2020_07
Lat: 35.158776 N
Long: 106.740105 W

